

Supplementary Information

Expanding the genome-targeting scope and the site selectivity of high-precision base editors

Tan et al.

Supplementary Table 1 Target protospacer sequences analyzed in this study. Target Cs are shown in red, with the subscript numbers indicating their position relative to the PAM. The PAM sequence is shown in blue.

Target	Sequence (5' → 3')	Analysis method
Can1-1	ATACTAAT ^{C-12} ^{C-11} ATGCCGCCAGTGG	canavanine selection
Can1-2	GCAAATT ^{C-13} AAATATTTACGTTGG	canavanine selection
Can1-3	ACGT ^{C-16} ^{C-15} AAAATTGAATGACTTGG	canavanine selection
Can1-4	TTT ^{C-17} AAGGTAAGTACTGACTAGTTGG	canavanine selection
Can1-5	T ^{C-19} ^{C-18} AATAACGGAATCCAAGTGG	canavanine selection
PolyC-1-NGA	A ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} ^{C-13} ^{C-12} TCATCTTTGAGTGA	NGS
PolyC-2-NGA	^{C-20} ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} TGAGGCTTATGAGAGA	NGS
PolyC-3-NGCG	T ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} TTCTGCCCAATTAGGCG	NGS
PolyC-4-NGCG	TTC ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} ^{C-13} ACTCACAGGAAGAGCG	NGS
PolyC-5-NGC	A ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} AAC ^{C-12} ^{C-11} ^{C-10} ^{C-9} ^{C-8} ^{C-7} ^{C-6} ATCAGTGC	NGS
PolyC-6-NGT	^{C-20} ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} ^{C-13} ^{C-12} TTGATACTTCCTGT	NGS
PolyC-7	^{C-21} ^{C-20} ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} ^{C-13} ATGTT ^{C-7} ^{C-6} GA GATCGG	NGS
PolyC-8	TATAC ^{C-20} ^{C-19} ^{C-18} ^{C-17} ^{C-16} ^{C-15} ^{C-14} ^{C-13} TATATGGTAAAAAGG	NGS
PSEN1-L166P	GCC ^{C-18} TATTATATCATCTCTATTGT	-
TYR-Y327C	ATTCAC ^{C-15} ATTGGGTCAAAGTCAAGG	-

Supplementary Table 2 Width of the editing windows of A3A-derived BEs in two polycytidine motifs (polyC-7 and polyC-8; cf. Fig. 2). The approximate width of the editing window was defined as the number of nucleotides within which editing efficiency exceeds the half-maximal value (21).

Base editor	PolyC-7	PolyC-8
A3A-BE3	5	6
A3A-NL-BE3	9	7
A3A Δ 194-BE3	4	4
A3A Δ 190-BE3	6	3
A3A Δ 186-BE3	4	2
A3A Δ 182-BE3	3	2
A3A Δ 178-BE3	3	2

Supplementary Table 3 Oligonucleotides used in this study.

Primers for construction of sgRNA plasmids

Primer name	Sequence (5' → 3')
sgRNA-Can1-1	AAAGATAAATGATCGATACTAATCCATGCCGCCAGGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA-Can1-2	AAAGATAAATGATCGGCAAATTCAAATATTTACGTGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA-Can1-3	AAAGATAAATGATCGACGTCCAAAATTGAATGACTGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA-Can1-4	AAAGATAAATGATCGTTTCAAGGTACTGAACTAGTGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA-Can1-5	AAAGATAAATGATCGTCCAATAACGGAATCCAACCTGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA-PolyC-1	AAAGATAAATGATCGACCCCCCCTCATCTTTGAGGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-2	AAAGATAAATGATCGCCCCCCTGAGGCTTATGAGGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-3	AAAGATAAATGATCGTCCCCCCTTCTGCCCAATTAGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-4	AAAGATAAATGATCGTTCCCCCCTCACAGGAAGGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-5	AAAGATAAATGATCGACCCCCAACCCCCCATCAGGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-6	AAAGATAAATGATCGCCCCCCTTGATACTTCCGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-7	AAAGATAAATGATCGCCCCCCTATGTTCCGAGATGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA- PolyC-8	AAAGATAAATGATCGCCCCCCTATATGGTAAAAGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGT
sgRNA-Rev	TATAGGGCGAATTGGGTACCGGCCGCAAATTAAG

Primers for construction of base editors

Primer name	Sequence (5' → 3')	Constructs
VQR-BE3-1F	GGACAAGGGTAGGGATTTCCG	VQR-BE3
VQR-BE3-1R	GAATCCGCCGTATTTCTTGG	
VQR-BE3-2F	CCAAGAAATACGGCGGATTCGTTTCTCCTACAGTCGCTTACAG	
VQR-BE3-2R	CAGGACCTCCTTTGTAGATCTGTATTGCTTTCTGTCTATGGTGGTGT	
VQR-BE3-3F	GATCTACAAAGGAGGTCCTG	
VQR-BE3-3R	TTGAATAACTAAAGCCCATG	
VRER-BE3-1F	GGACAAGGGTAGGGATTTCCG	VRER-BE3
VRER-BE3-1R	ACCTTTCTGCAGCTCGCGCGCACTAGCGAGCAT	
VRER-BE3-2F	GAGCTGCAGAAAGGTAACGA	
VRER-BE3-2R	CTTTGTAGATCTGTATTCCTTTCTGTCTATGGT	
VRER-BE3-3F	TACAGATCTACAAAGGAGGT	
VRER-BE3-3R	ATGTTACATGCGTACACGCG	

Cas9NG-BE3-1F	GGACAAGGGTAGGGATTTCCG	Cas9-NG-BE3
Cas9NG-BE3-1R	GCTGTTCCTTTTCGGGCGGATACTTTCTTGGGA	
Cas9NG-BE3-2F	CCGAAAAGGAACAGCGACAA	
Cas9NG-BE3-2R	GTTACCTTTCTGCAGGAAGCGCGCACTAGCGAGCAT	
Cas9NG-BE3-3F	CTGCAGAAAGGTAACGAGCT	
Cas9NG-BE3-3R	AAGTACTTGAAGGCTCGAGGCGGCCCAAGTT	
Cas9NG-BE3-4F	GCCTTCAAGTACTTCGACACCACCATAGACAGAAAGGTATACAGATCTACAAAG GAGG	
Cas9NG-BE3-4R	ATGTTACATGCGTACACGCG	
cCDA1v-1F	GGACAAGGGTAGGGATTTCCG	cCDA1-VQR/VRER/NG-BE3
cCDA1v-1R	CAGATTCAGAAGTACCTGGAGTTTCAGAACCAGAGTCTCCACCGAGCTGAGAG A	
cCDA1v-2F	TCCAGGTACTTCTGAATCTGCTACTCCAGAATCTATGACCGACGCTGAGTACGT GAG	
cCDA1v-2R	ATTTGCAGGCATTTGCTCGGCATGCCGGTAGAGGTGTGGT	
A3A-NL-1F	AGAAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCCGGGAAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A-NL-BE3
A3A-NL-1R	TCTTGTCCATGTTTCCCTGATTCTGGAGAA	
A3A-NL-2F	TCAGGGAAACATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A-NL-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3B-NL-1F	AGAAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCCGGGAAAAAAATGAATC CACAGATCAGAAA	A3B-NL-BE3
A3B-NL-1R	TCTTGTCCATGTTTCCCTGATTCTGGAGAA	
A3B-NL-2F	TCAGGGAAACATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3B-NL-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
hAID-NL-1F	AGAAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCCGGGAAAAAAATGGACA GCCTCTTGATGAA	hAID-NL-BE3
hAID -NL-1R	TCTTGTCCATAAGTCCCAAAGTACGAAATG	
hAID -NL-2F	TTTGGGACTTATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
hAID -NL-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
mAID-NL-1F	AGAAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCCGGGAAAAAAATGGACA GCCTTCTGATGAA	mAID-NL-BE3
mAID -NL-1R	TCTTGTCCATAAATCCCAACATACGAAATG	
mAID -NL-2F	GTTGGGATTTATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	

mAID -NL-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
cAICDA -NL-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGAGCA AGCTGGACAGTGT	cAICDA-NL- BE3
cAICDA -NL-1R	TCTTGTCCATAAGGCCAGCAGAGCGAAGC	
cAICDA -NL-2F	GCTGGGCCTTATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
cAICDA -NL-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3G -NL-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGAAAC CGCATTTTCGCAA	A3G-NL-BE3
A3G -NL-1R	TCTTGTCCATATTTTCTGGTTTTGCAGGA	
A3G -NL-2F	CCAGGAAAATATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3G -NL-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A-BE3
A3A -1R	CAGATTCAGAAGTACCTGGAGTTTCAGAACCAGAGTTTCCCTGATTCTGGAGA A	
A3A-2F	TCCAGGTA CTCTGAATCTGCTACTCCAGAATCTATGGACAAGAAGTACTCC	
A3A-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A194-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A Δ 194- BE3
A3A194 -1R	TCTTGTCCATGAGAATGGCCCGCAGCCTCC	
A3A194-2F	GGCATTCTCATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A194-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A190-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A Δ 190- BE3
A3A190 -1R	TCTTGTCCATCAGCCTCCACTCAGGGCTT	
A3A190-2F	TGGGAGGCTGATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A190-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A186-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A Δ 186- BE3
A3A186 -1R	TCTTGTCCATCAGGGCTTGGCTGTGCTCAT	
A3A186-2F	CCAAGCCCTGATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A186-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A182-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAACTAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A Δ 182- BE3
A3A182 -1R	TCTTGTCCATGTGCTCATCTAGTCCATCCC	

A3A182-2F	AGATGAGCACATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A182-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A178-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAAGTACTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A Δ 178- BE3
A3A178 -1R	TCTTGTCCATTCCATCCCAGGGCTGGAAGG	
A3A178-2F	CTGGGATGGAATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A178-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
A3A154-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAAGTACTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	A3A Δ 154- BE3
A3A154 -1R	TCTTGTCCATGGTCATGATGGAGACTTGGG	
A3A154-2F	CATCATGACCATGGACAAGAAGTACTCCAT	
A3A154-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
eA3A-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAAGTACTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGGAAG CCAGCCCAGCATC	eA3A-BE3
eA3A-1R	AAGATTCTTAGCCTGGCCGTGTAGAAAGCCCCTGTGC	
eA3A-2F	CAGGCTAAGAATCTTCTCTG	
eA3A-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
R128A-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAAGTACTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGAGTT CCGAGACAGGC	A3A(R128A)- BE3
R128A-1R	TCGTAATCATAGATGGCGGCAGCGAAGATACG	
R128A-2F	CATCTATGATTACGACCCCC	
R128A-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	
Y130F-1F	AGAAAAACCCCGGATTCTAGAAGTACTGGATCCCCGGGAAAAAATGAGTT CCGAGACAGGC	A3A(Y130F)- BE3
Y130F-1R	AGGGGGTCGTAATCAAAGATGCGGGCAGCGA	
Y130F-2F	TGATTACGACCCCCTATATA	
Y130F-2R	ATTACTAAAGATCTCCTGCAGGTAGCAGATCCGATTCTTTC	

Primers for amplification of target regions for high-throughput sequencing (HTS)

Primer name	Sequence (5' → 3')
PolyC-1-HTS-index1-F	ATCACGGGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC
PolyC-1-HTS-index1-R	GCCTAATTTTATAAATTTTGGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-1-HTS-index2-F	CGATGTGGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC
PolyC-1-HTS-index2-R	TGGTCATTTTATAAATTTTGGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-1-HTS-index3-F	AGTTCCGGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC

PolyC-1-HTS-index3-R	CTCTACTTTTATAAATTTTGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-1-HTS-index4-F	CACTCAGGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC
PolyC-1-HTS-index4-R	TGTTGGTTTTATAAATTTTGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-1-HTS-index5-F	GTGGCCGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC
PolyC-1-HTS-index5-R	CGAAACTTTTATAAATTTTGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-1-HTS-index6-F	CGTACGGGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC
PolyC-1-HTS-index6-R	CCACTCTTTTATAAATTTTGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-1-HTS-index7-F	GGTAGCGGAAAGACTGGCTCATCAAACC
PolyC-1-HTS-index7-R	ATCAGTTTTTATAAATTTTGAGGAAGCG
PolyC-2-HTS-index1-F	CACCGGTGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index1-R	ATCGTGTGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-2-HTS-index2-F	ATGAGCTGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index2-R	AGGAATTGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-2-HTS-index3-F	CAAAGTGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index3-R	TAGTTGTGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-2-HTS-index4-F	TCGGCATGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index4-R	GAATGATGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-2-HTS-index5-F	TCCCGATGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index5-R	CTTCGATGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-2-HTS-index6-F	CTATACTGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index6-R	TCTGAGTGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-2-HTS-index7-F	TTAGGCTGCGCACATCAATCATTTTC
PolyC-2-HTS-index7-R	TGACCATGGCTTACTGTAAGCTACAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index1-F	ACATGTTCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index1-R	CAGATCCTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index2-F	ACTTGATCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index2-R	GATCAGCTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index3-F	TAGCTTTCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index3-R	GGCTACCTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index4-F	CCGTCCTCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index4-R	GTAGAGCTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index5-F	GTCCGCTCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index5-R	GTGAAACTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index6-F	GTTTCGTCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index6-R	GAGTGGCTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-3-HTS-index7-F	ACTGATTCCGCCATGTCCAACACG
PolyC-3-HTS-index7-R	ATTCCTCTTTAATAATTTCCGAAATAGG
PolyC-4-HTS-index1-F	CAACTAGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC
PolyC-4-HTS-index1-R	CACGATTGACCCAAAGGGAAACATAAGAC
PolyC-4-HTS-index2-F	CAGGCGGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC

PolyC-4-HTS-index2-R	CATGGCTGACCCAAAGGGAACATAAGAC
PolyC-4-HTS-index3-F	ACAGTGGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC
PolyC-4-HTS-index3-R	GCCAATTGACCCAAAGGGAACATAAGAC
PolyC-4-HTS-index4-F	CTTGTAGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC
PolyC-4-HTS-index4-R	AGTCAATGACCCAAAGGGAACATAAGAC
PolyC-4-HTS-index5-F	ATGTCAGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC
PolyC-4-HTS-index5-R	CATTTTTGACCCAAAGGGAACATAAGAC
PolyC-4-HTS-index6-F	CCAACAGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC
PolyC-4-HTS-index6-R	CGGAATTGACCCAAAGGGAACATAAGAC
PolyC-4-HTS-index7-F	TCATTCGGGAAAATAAAGGGAAAGACC
PolyC-4-HTS-index7-R	CTAGCTTGACCCAAAGGGAACATAAGAC
PolyC-5-HTS-index1-F	CACCGGGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index1-R	ATCGTGAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index2-F	ATGAGCGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index2-R	AGGAATAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index3-F	CAAAGGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index3-R	TAGTTGAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index4-F	TCGGCAGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index4-R	GAATGAAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index5-F	TCCCGAGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index5-R	CTTCGAAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index6-F	CTATACGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index6-R	TCTGAGAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index7-F	TTAGGCGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index7-R	TGACCAAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index8-F	ACATGTGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index8-R	CAGATCAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index9-F	ACTTGAGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index9-R	GATCAGAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index10-F	TAGCTTGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index10-R	GGCTACAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index11-F	CCGTCCGTCACACCACGCTCAAACGG
PolyC-5-HTS-index11-R	GTAGAGAGATCTGGTCCACGGCCTGG
PolyC-6-HTS-index1-F	GTCCGCTTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG
PolyC-6-HTS-index1-R	GTGAAAGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-6-HTS-index2-F	GTTTCGTTTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG
PolyC-6-HTS-index2-R	GAGTGGGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-6-HTS-index3-F	ACTGATTTTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG
PolyC-6-HTS-index3-R	ATTCCTGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-6-HTS-index4-F	CAACTATTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG

PolyC-6-HTS-index4-R	CACGATGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-6-HTS-index5-F	CAGGCGTTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG
PolyC-6-HTS-index5-R	CATGGCGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-6-HTS-index6-F	ACAGTGTTTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG
PolyC-6-HTS-index6-R	GCCAATGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-6-HTS-index7-F	CTTGATTCGGGGTTATTTATTTTTCG
PolyC-6-HTS-index7-R	AGTCAAGTTTGATTGGTCAAGTTGGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index1-F	CGATGTACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index1-R	TGGTCATATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index2-F	ATCACGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index2-R	GCCTAATATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index3-F	AGTTCCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index3-R	CTCTACTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index4-F	CACTCAACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index4-R	TGTTGGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index5-F	GTGGCCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index5-R	CGAAACTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index6-F	CGTACGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index6-R	CCACTCTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index7-F	GGTAGCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index7-R	ATCAGTTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index8-F	CACCGGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index8-R	ATCGTGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index9-F	ATGAGCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index9-R	AGGAATTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index10-F	CAAAGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index10-R	TAGTTGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index11-F	TCGGCAACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index11-R	GAATGATATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index12-F	TCCCGAACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index12-R	CTTCGATATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index13-F	CTATACACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index13-R	TCTGAGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index14-F	TTAGGCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index14-R	TGACCATATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index15-F	ACATGTACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index15-F	CAGATCTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index16-F	ACTTGAAGTACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index16-R	GATCAGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index17-F	TAGCTTACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC

PolyC-7-HTS-index17-R	GGCTACTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index18-F	CCGTCCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index18-R	GTAGAGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index19-F	GTCCGCACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index19-R	GTGAAATATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index20-F	GTTTCGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index20-R	GAGTGGTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index21-F	ACTGATACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index21-R	ATTCCTTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index22-F	CAACTAACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index22-R	CACGATTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index23-F	CAGGCGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index23-R	CATGGCTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-7-HTS-index24-F	ACAGTGACTGCGGAAGTGAGGGGAGC
PolyC-7-HTS-index24-R	GCCAATTATCCGTGCGCGTAATCCTTCT
PolyC-8-HTS-index1-F	ATCACGTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index1-R	CGATGTATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index2-F	TTAGGCTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index2-R	TGACCAATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index3-F	ACAGTGTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index3-R	GCCAATATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index4-F	CAGATCTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index4-R	ACTTGAATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index5-F	GATCAGTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index5-R	TAGCTTATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index6-F	GGCTACTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index6-R	CTTGTAATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index7-F	AGTCAATTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index7-R	AGTTCCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index8-F	ATGTCATTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index8-R	CCGTCCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index9-F	GTAGAGTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index9-R	GTCCGCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index10-F	GTGAAATTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index10-R	GTGGCCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index11-F	GTTTCGTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index11-R	CGTACGATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index12-F	GAGTGGTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index12-R	GGTAGCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index13-F	ACTGATTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG

PolyC-8-HTS-index13-R	ATGAGCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index14-F	ATTCCTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index14-R	CAAAAGATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index15-F	CAACTATTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index15-R	CACCGGATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index16-F	CACGATTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index16-R	CACTCAATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index17-F	CAGGCGTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index17-R	CATGGCATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index18-F	CATTTTTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index18-R	CCAACAATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index19-F	CGGAATTTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index19-R	CTAGCTATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index20-F	CTATACTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index20-R	CTCAGAATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG
PolyC-8-HTS-index21-F	GACGACTTCATCTATAAGGATATGGGTTCG
PolyC-8-HTS-index21-R	TAATCGATAGCATATAATAAAAAGTGGAG

Supplementary Figure 1 Analysis of base editing of a set of VQR-Cas9 BEs fused to the full-length CDA1 (nCDA1-VQRBE3) or C-terminally truncated versions of CDA1 (nCDA1Δ195-VQRBE3; nCDA1Δ194-VQRBE3; nCDA1Δ193-VQRBE3; nCDA1Δ192-VQRBE3; nCDA1Δ190-VQRBE3; nCDA1Δ188-VQRBE3; Fig. 1a,c). The two tested target sequences (PolyC-1-NGA and PolyC-2-NGA) both contain a polyC stretch upstream of the

PAM sequence NGA that is recognized by VQR-Cas9 (Fig. 1b). The amplified target sequences were directly sequenced by the dideoxy chain termination method (see Methods), and the sequence chromatograms are shown for each BE. The nucleotide sequences are shown above the chromatograms, with the PAM indicated in blue and the positions of the cytidines in the polyC stretch given in red (relative to the PAM). The reciprocal full-length fusion, cCDA1-VQRBE3, was also analyzed. nCDA1-BE3 and cCDA1-BE3 have no PAM in proper distance from the polyC stretch and served as negative controls.

Supplementary Figure 2 Analysis of base editing of a set of VRER-Cas9 BEs fused to the full-length CDA1 (nCDA1-VRERBE3) or C-terminally truncated versions of CDA1 (nCDA1Δ195-VRERBE3; nCDA1Δ194-VRERBE3; nCDA1Δ193-VRERBE3; nCDA1Δ192-VRERBE3; nCDA1Δ190-VRERBE3; nCDA1Δ188-VRERBE3; Fig. 1a,d). The two tested target sequences (PolyC-3-NGCG and PolyC-4-NGCG) both contain a polyC stretch upstream of the PAM sequence NGCG that is recognized by VRER-Cas9 (Fig. 1b). The amplified target sequences were directly sequenced by the dideoxy chain termination method (see Methods), and the sequence chromatograms are shown for each BE. The nucleotide sequences are shown above the chromatograms, with the PAM indicated in blue and the positions of the cytidines in the polyC stretch given in red (relative to the PAM). The reciprocal full-length fusion, cCDA1-VRERBE3, was also analyzed. nCDA1-BE3 and cCDA1-BE3 have no PAM in proper distance from the polyC stretch and served as negative controls.

Supplementary Figure 3 Analysis of base editing of a set of xCas9 BEs fused to the full-length CDA1 (nCDA1-xBE3) or C-terminally truncated versions of CDA1 (nCDA1Δ195-xBE3; nCDA1Δ194-xBE3; nCDA1Δ193-xBE3; nCDA1Δ192-xBE3; nCDA1Δ190-xBE3; nCDA1Δ188-xBE3; Fig. 1a,e). The tested target sequence (PolyC-5-NGC) contains a polyC stretch upstream of the PAM sequence NG that is recognized by xCas9 (Fig. 1b). The amplified target sequences were directly sequenced by the dideoxy chain termination method (see Methods), and the sequence chromatograms are shown for each BE. The nucleotide sequence is shown above the chromatograms, with the PAM indicated in blue and the positions of the cytidines in the polyC stretch given in red (relative to the PAM). The

reciprocal full-length fusion, cCDA1-xBE3, was also analyzed. nCDA1-BE3 and cCDA1-BE3 have no PAM in proper distance from the polyC stretch and served as negative controls.

Supplementary Figure 4 Analysis of base editing of a set of SpCas9-NG BEs fused to the full-length CDA1 (nCDA1-NGBE3) or C-terminally truncated versions of CDA1 (nCDA1Δ195-NGBE3; nCDA1Δ194-NGBE3; nCDA1Δ193-NGBE3; nCDA1Δ192-NGBE3;

nCDA1 Δ 190-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 188-NGBE3; Fig. 1a,f,g). The three tested target sequences (PolyC-1-NGA, PolyC-5-NGC and PolyC-6-NGT) all contain a polyC stretch upstream of the PAM sequence NG that is recognized by SpCas9-NG (Fig. 1b). The amplified target sequences were directly sequenced by the dideoxy chain termination method (see Methods), and the sequence chromatograms are shown for each BE. The nucleotide sequences are shown above the chromatograms, with the PAM indicated in blue and the positions of the cytidines in the polyC stretch given in red (relative to the PAM). The reciprocal full-length fusion, cCDA1-NGBE3, was also analyzed. nCDA1-BE3 and cCDA1-BE3 have no PAM in proper distance from the polyC stretch and served as negative controls.

Supplementary Figure 5 Base editing outcomes of cCDA1-VQRBE3, cCDA1-VRERBE3 and BE variants with SpCas9-VQR or SpCas9-VRER fusions to C-terminally truncated CDA1 variants. Two NGA target sites were tested (PolyC-1-NGA, PolyC-2-NGA; for sequences see Supplementary Table 1; for sequence chromatograms, see Supplementary Figure 1) for BEs with SpCas9-VQR and two NGCG target sites were tested (PolyC-3-NGCG, PolyC-4-NGCG; for sequences see Supplementary Table 1; for sequence chromatograms, see Supplementary Figure 2) for BEs with SpCas9-VRER. For comparison, the cCDA1-BE3 editor (recognizing the PAM sequence NGG) was also included. % of C-to-T editing represents the percentage of total sequencing reads with the target C converted to T. Values and error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of three independent biological replicates. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

PolyC-1-NGA

PolyC-5-NGC

PolyC-6-NGT

Supplementary Figure 6 Base editing outcomes of cCDA1-NGBE3, cCDA1-xBE3 and BE variants with SpCas9-NG or xCas9 fusions to C-terminally truncated CDA1 variants. Three non-NGG target sites were tested (PolyC-1-NGA, PolyC-5-NGC and PolyC-6-NGT; for sequences see Supplementary Table 1; for sequence chromatograms, see Supplementary Figures 3 and 4). For comparison the cCDA1-BE3 editor (recognizing the PAM sequence NGG) was also included. % of C-to-T editing represents the percentage of total sequencing reads with the target C converted to T. Values and error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of three independent biological replicates. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 7 Analysis of base editing of a set of SpCas9-NG BEs fused to the full-length CDA1 (nCDA1-NGBE3) or C-terminally truncated versions of CDA1

(nCDA1 Δ 195-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 194-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 193-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 192-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 190-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 188-NGBE3) in two target sequences containing the PAM sequence NGG (PolyC-7, PolyC-8). Both target sequences contain a polyC stretch upstream of the PAM. Note that the PAM sequence NGG can be recognized by both the wild-type Cas9 (as in nCDA1-BE3 and cCDA1-BE3) and the SpCas9-NG variants. The amplified target sequences were directly sequenced by the dideoxy chain termination method (see Methods), and the sequence chromatograms are shown for each BE. The nucleotide sequences are shown above the chromatograms, with the PAM indicated in blue and the positions of the cytidines in the polyC stretch given in red (relative to the PAM). The reciprocal full-length fusion, cCDA1-NGBE3, was also analyzed.

PolyC-7 CTTTCCCCCCCCATGTTCCGAGATCGG
4-26-18-17-16-15-14-13 7-8

PolyC-8 TATACCCCCCTATATGGTAAAAAGG
20-18-17-16-15-14-13

Supplementary Figure 8 Quantitative analysis of base editing outcomes obtained with a set of SpCas9-NG BEs fused to the full-length CDA1 (nCDA1-NGBE3) or C-terminally truncated versions of CDA1 (nCDA1 Δ 194-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 193-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 192-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 190-NGBE3; nCDA1 Δ 188-NGBE3) in comparison to the two full-length CDA1 fusions to the wild-type Cas9 (nCDA1-BE3; cCDA1-BE3). Both tested target sequences contain the PAM sequence NGG (PolyC-7, PolyC-8). The nucleotide sequences are shown above the diagrams, with the PAM indicated in blue and the positions of the cytidines in the polyC stretch given in red (relative to the PAM). % of C-to-T editing represents the percentage of total sequencing reads with the target C converted to T. Values and error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of three independent biological replicates. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

a

b

Supplementary Figure 9 Screening of deaminases directly fused to Cas9 (without linkers) for efficient base editing. **a** Series of new BEs constructed by directly fusing different APOBEC and AID deaminases with the Cas9 nickase (nCas9) and the uracil DNA glycosylase inhibitor (UGI) when targeting two polyC sites (polyC-7 and polyC-8). **b** Base editing outcomes of new BEs when targeting two polyC sites (polyC-7 and polyC-8). The sequence of each target site is shown with the numbers indicating the position of possible editing targets (red) relative to the PAM (blue). % of C-to-T editing represents the percentage of total sequencing reads with the target C converted to T. Values and error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of three independent biological replicates. hA3A: human *APOBEC3A* (GenBank accession number NM_145699); hA3B: human *APOBEC3B* (NM_004900); hA3G: human *APOBEC3G* (NM_021822); hAID: human *AID* (NM_020661); mAID: mouse *AID* (NM_009645); cAICDA: channel catfish *AICDA* (NM_001200185). Source data underlying panels **b** are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 10 Removal of the linker between A3A and nCas9 broadens the width of the editing window while not appreciably affecting editing efficiency. Two polyC target sequences (polyC-7 and polyC-8; see Supplementary Figure 9) were tested. The x-axis shows the target Cs and their positions relative to the PAM. % of C-to-T editing represents the percentage of total sequencing reads with the target C converted to T. Values and error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of three independent biological replicates. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

Supplementary Figure 11 Design of base editors with truncated A3A domains. **a** Amino acid sequence alignment of A3A and CDA1. The catalytic domain is indicated by the black horizontal line. The alignment was created by CLUSTAL W (ref. 43; <https://www.genome.jp/tools-bin/clustalw>) and graphically formatted with the help of the ESPript 3.0 server (ref. 44; <http://esprict.ibcp.fr/ESPript/ESPript/>). Identical amino acid residues are marked in red, similar residues in yellow. **b** Schematic representation of BEs with C-terminal A3A truncations. The truncated variants are named after the last A3A residue included.

Supplementary Figure 12 Base editing outcomes of A3A-BE3, two narrow-window A3AΔ-BE3 variants, two recently reported mutant BE3 variants that reduce off-target RNA editing (A3A(R128A)-BE3, A3A(Y130F)-BE3; 33) and the combinations of these mutations with each of the two narrow-window A3AΔ-BE3 variants. Five sites in the yeast *Can1* gene (containing Cs at different positions) were targeted and their sequences are listed in Supplementary Table 1. Edited clones were identified by using the canavanine selection strategy (see Methods). The x-axis represents the target Cs within the protospacers. The y-axis shows their C-to-T editing frequencies (see Methods). Values and error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of three independent biological replicates. Source data are provided as a Source Data file.

a

Supplementary Figure 13 Analysis of off-target editing induced by base editors nCDA1-BE3, cCDA1-BE3 and nCDA1 Δ 190-BE3 in yeast. **a** Schematic representation of the three base editors. **b** Experimental workflow.

Supplementary Figure 14 Fraction of pathogenic T-to-C and A-to-G SNPs in the ClinVar database (5074 mutations in total; ref. 8) that can be precisely addressed by the BEs available previously (left) and the expanded set of BEs that includes the high-precision BEs developed in the course of this work (right). The editing windows were assumed as follows: BE3 and A3A-BE3: C₋₁₃ to C₋₁₇; cCDA1-BE3: C₋₁₆ to C₋₁₉; nCDA1-BE3: C₋₁₄ to C₋₂₀ (refs. 15, 22, 23). The BE variants described in this work, including the A3A Δ -BE3 and nCDA1 Δ -BE3 mutants, were assumed to have a narrowed window (C₋₁₅ to C₋₁₆) recognizing the PAM NGG and an editing preference of C₋₁₈ > C₋₁₇ > C₋₁₉ recognizing the PAM NG, respectively.